

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY OF HYGROTHERMAL AGING OF A SHORT HEMP FIBERS /POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITE

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Abstract - The kinetic of isothermal water absorption of injected polypropylene reinforced short hemp fibers specimens is studied for four immersion temperatures (20, 40, 60, 80°C). The experimental results do not obey the Fick model based on a constant coefficient of diffusion and the time to reach the saturation level of water absorption decreases significantly with temperature. Thus, a new analytical model is proposed, using a variable coefficient of diffusion, which is used in analytical and FEA simulations. The results obtained show a very good correlation between experimental, analytical and FEA absorption curves.

1 Introduction

In addition to be recyclable, natural fiber reinforced polymer composites (NFC, bio-based composites) have interesting mechanical properties and can rival with conventional non-degradable materials for some applications. However, the major obstacles to the development of the NFC are the environment effects, namely: heat, ultraviolet radiation and moisture that can cause premature deterioration of structures and make them inadequate to fulfill their function. Moreover, the heterogeneity of composite materials makes the study of the ageing process and damage more complex, especially in the case of injected thermoplastic matrixes reinforced with vegetable fibers. The hydrophilic behavior of the reinforcements opposes the hydrophobicity of the matrix, thereby generating different absorption mechanisms. Generally, the presence of water in composites has adverse effects on its mechanical properties.

The absorption of water by this type of materials usually evolves in two steps: a first linear stage characterized by a constant diffusion coefficient D , and a second one for which the moisture of the material reaches a maximum level characterized by a

saturation plateau. This interaction of water molecules with the material is generally described by Fick's second law [1]. The kinetics of moisture diffusion in composite materials depends on several parameters i.e. fibers' nature (chemical composition, geometry, volume fraction, variability), matrix properties, presence of porosities and quality of fiber/matrix's adhesion. The time required to reach saturation is dependent on the surrounding temperature and environment (water purity, moisture percentage) in which the material evolves.

Several studies have examined the diffusion of moisture in composite materials. Jost [2] has used Fick's model with a constant coefficient of diffusion. Similarly, Kushwaha and Kumar[3] found a Fickian behavior of water diffusion in bamboo-polyester composites. The study of hybrid materials e.g. polypropylene / hemp / glass by Panthapulakkal and Sain [4] showed an absorption obeying to Fick's diffusion model.

However, Fick's diffusion law cannot be generalized and specific cases of diffusion are governed differently. For illustration, different types of non-Fickian behaviors are compared to typical Fick's curve in Fig.1.

- curve (0): Fickian absorption behavior;
- curve (1): pseudo-Fickian behavior for which equilibrium is never reached;
- curve (2): Langmuir-type kinetics;
- curve (3): absorption followed by material damage at saturation;
- curve (4): weight loss after a certain period of aging (presence of physical damage, chemical or material hydrolysis).

It is accepted that the kinetics of diffusion is not considered as Fickian if the initial trend (less than 60% of the saturation mass) of the absorption curve as function of the square root of time is not linear [5]. Among non Fickian models, Langmuir's model [6] exhibits two saturation stages (Fig.1). For cases where the diffusivity is a variable function over the time, Weitsman [7] have proposed a diffusion coefficient depending on time and temperature. Yeh et al.[8] have presented a study of diffusion with two levels in order to describe the adsorption behavior of the humidity in a cyanate ester resin. In this work, authors have considered the first stage as Fickian and the second one characterized by a decreasing diffusion coefficient over time. We will see along the next paragraphs that, in the context of the work presented here, a model with variable diffusivity over time appears to be the most appropriate.

Fig 1. Schematic curves representing 4 non-Fickian kinetics of water absorption [9].

In Fig.1, M_s is the moisture content at saturation while M_t is the moisture content at time t . The present work aims at the modeling of the behavior of water aged short hemp fibers /polypropylene (PP) composites. The experimental data are compared to

predicted values to assess the validity of assumptions.

2 Experimental protocol

The material specimens tested are made of hemp/PP granules with a reinforcement volume fraction of 30% (Fig.2.a). Compounds were injected at the temperature of 180°C with a Billion electric thermoplastic injection machine of mold closing force capacity of 100 tons (Fig.2.b). The material considered in this work is a composite with a thermoplastic matrix (polypropylene) increased to 30% volume fraction of hemp short fibers. Molded tensile specimens were dumbbell shaped with a central zone's length of 50 mm, with width and thickness of respectively 10 and 4 mm as nominal dimensions, in conformity with ISO 294 standard (Fig.2.c). 40mm × 150mm × 10mm tensile specimens (alters) are produced by injection of granules composed of polypropylene and short fibers of hemp (see Fig.2.a) according to the standard (ISO 294-1). Fig.2.b shows the injection machine used for the manufacture of test specimens.

Fig.2. a) Hemp/polypropylene granules, b) Electric injection machine and c) injected tensile specimen.

The aging tests were performed in a thermo-stated bath containing distilled water. The specimens were oven dried at 75°C for 24 hours before immersion in distilled water at 4 temperatures (20, 40, 60 and 80 °C) according to the ASTM D570-98 standard. The samples were weighted every day on a regular basis on a balance with 10^{-3} g accuracy. The effects of water absorption on the evolution of mechanical properties of the material were measured by

monotonic and cyclic tensile tests. Tensile tests are performed with rate of 2 mm/s, by means of the INSTON type tensile machine, equipped with a load cell with a maximum capacity of 150 KN. Several parameters can be acquired simultaneously (time, applied load, deformation). Specimens were placed between the jaws of the tensile testing machine while taking care of vertical alignment and a strain gauge is used.

3 Diffusion of moisture and thermal analogy

The considered model the kinetics of water absorption in composite materials is Fick's model given in relation (1). C represents the local concentration of humidity, D the diffusion coefficient, (x, y, z) the material coordinates and t time.

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D_x \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + D_z \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \quad (1)$$

Considering the material homogeneous and isotropic and assuming that diffusion mainly occurs along the specimen's thickness $D_x = D_y = D_z = D$ and equation (1) simplifies to relation (2).

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

This equation is analogous to the differential equation of heat diffusion, which by the way can also be used to model the diffusion of moisture in materials. Thus, Fick's law can be solved by analogy with the thermal diffusion phenomenon [1-3] given in equation (3). The temperature (T) and thermal diffusivity (α) are respectively comparable to C and D parameters in relation (2).

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

Thanks to the analogy between equations (2) and (3), the modeling of Fickian moisture diffusion can be solved using a heat transfer Finite Element Analysis (FEA) solver [4]. The only restriction in doing that is the fact that both moisture and

temperature diffusion cannot be solved together. In our case, temperature is considered as constant with space coordinates and time (for the specimens and distilled water used for immersion).

4 Experimental results and discussion

In order to measure the water absorption, the composite specimens have been weighted daily and the moisture absorption calculated as the relative weight uptake (see equation 4 from [10]).

$$M(\%) = \left(\frac{m_f - m_0}{m_0} \right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where

$M(\%)$: water absorption percentage

m_f : mass of the aging specimen

m_0 : mass of the dry specimen

Fig.3 presents the evolution of water absorption as a function of the square root of days for specimens immersed in distilled water at 4 different temperatures (20, 40, 60 and 80 °C). The curves clearly show variations in the slope or the rate of diffusion depending on water temperature when all facets of the specimens are in contact with water. Indeed, the rate of diffusion increases with water temperature. This can be explained by the outbreak of several types of diffusion with increasing temperature that accompanies the rapid degradation of the fibers and fiber-matrix interface [11].

On the other hand, saturation levels are about the same for each temperature. The time required to reach saturation depends on the rate of penetration of the water particles in the material and consequently of the material's temperature.

As shown in Fig.1 (curve 0), in the case of a purely Fickian behavior, the first stage of the absorption curve is linear and the diffusion coefficient D is constant.

This coefficient is calculated from the slope of the absorption curve between time t_1 and t_2 as follows [1, 10]:

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_s} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

M_1 and M_2 are the water uptake at times t_1 and t_2 respectively, M_s is the water uptake at saturation and h is the specimen's thickness.

Fig.3. Moisture uptake over the square root of time for samples immersed in water at four different temperatures.

Fig.3 shows that, in our experiments, the slope of these absorption curves, and by the way the diffusion coefficient, is clearly not constant. This highlights that the behavior associated with these water absorption curves is not purely Fickian and it also suggests that the actual behavior could be modeled using a variable diffusion coefficient D as it is the case in some of the references mentioned in the introduction.

5 Analytical and FE solution of Fick's equation

Water absorption with time is obtained by solving the one-dimensional form of Fick's equation. The analytical solution of this equations is given by [9]:

$$M_t = M_s \left(1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{D(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{h^2}\right) \right) \quad (6)$$

This solution can be considered as a good first approximation in the case of thin specimens. This allows a validation of FEA results and it also allows quickly simulating the introduction of a varying diffusion coefficient in the model as presented in the next section.

As mentioned in the previous sections moisture diffusion with time can also be simulated with FEA,

using an analogy with thermal diffusion. We used a thermal solver along with a Visual Basic© macro aimed at calculating the evolution of water absorption with time from the transient moisture distribution field $C(x, y, z, t)$ as provided by FEA results.

Water absorption at time t can be calculated from the transient moisture distribution field $C(x, y, z, t)$ by integrating it over the specimen's volume V :

$$M_t = \iiint_V C(x, y, z, t) dx dy dz \quad (7)$$

This integral is calculated from 3D FEA results using a Gauss-Legendre quadrature [12].

The experimental and numerical evolutions of water absorption with time for a specimen immersed in 20, 40, 60, 80°C water as a function of time are compared in Fig. 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively. Overall, the moisture in both cases exhibits the same increase trend. However it can be noticed that the FEA results first over-estimate the water uptake, then numerical prediction becomes more accurate compared to the experimental measurements, near the saturation level. This difference can be explained by the fact that the actual behavior of water absorption in this material cannot be considered as exactly Fickian.

Fig.4. Experimental and finite element results of moisture content as a function of time in the case of immersion in water at 20°C.

Fig.5. Experimental and finite element results of moisture content as a function of time in the case of immersion in water at 40 °C.

Fig.6. Experimental and finite element results of moisture content as a function of time in the case of immersion in water at 60 °C.

Moreover, as introduced in the previous section, the shape of these experimental curves suggests that the actual diffusion coefficient (D) is not constant but increases during the absorption process.

Fig.8 shows FEA simulation results of the spatial distribution of moisture concentration versus time for a specimen that has been completely immersed and for which all facets are in contact with water at temperature 20° C. The specimen's dimensions are 150mm x 10mm x 4mm.

Fig.7. Experimental and finite element results of moisture content as a function of time in the case of immersion in water at 80 °C.

Fig.8. FEA simulation of the concentration with time across a section of a specimen that is immersed in water at 20 °C.

6 A new non-Fickian model

The observation of experimental results indicates that the diffusion kinetics studied is not Fickian and by the way, experimental results of diffusion cannot be represented using equation (6) with a constant diffusion coefficient D .

The variation of the diffusion coefficient with time can be explained by the physical and chemical phenomena that occur during the penetration of water into the composite. In the literature, several authors have studied the absorption of water by natural fiber composites and its effect on material's mechanical properties. The exposure to water of a composite reinforced by natural fibers known for their hydrophilic nature causes swelling in the fiber which causes micro cracks in the matrix and then the separation of the fiber-matrix interface, thereby creating additional passages for the water particles

which increases the rate of water penetration [11, 13]

Therefore, we propose replacing, in equation (6), the constant diffusion coefficient D by a new variable coefficient with time:

$$D(T, t) = D_0 e^{\omega t^2} \quad (8)$$

where

D_0 represents the initial diffusion coefficient and ω a corrective coefficient.

As illustrated just below, both D_0 and ω vary with the temperature of water immersion and the variation of these coefficients can be derived from the experiments at different immersion temperatures.

We have applied this new analytical model on the experimental data presented in previous sections for each temperature and Tab.1 summarizes parameter values obtained. In Tab.1 M_s , D_0 , R and T are respectively, the mass increase at saturation (in %), the initial diffusion coefficient, the ideal gases constant and water immersion temperature (in degrees Kelvin).

Tab.1. Diffusion parameters at different temperatures obtained from experimental data.

T (K)	293,15	313,15	333,15	353,15
M_s (%)	7.559	7.852	7.57	7.58
D_0 (mm ² /day)	$6.516 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.579 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.722 \cdot 10^{-1}$
ω (K ⁻¹ s ⁻²)	0.00003	0.0008	0.002	0.01
R (J/mol K)	8,31	8,31	8,31	8,31
d_0 (m ² /s)	0.0989	0.0989	0.0989	0.0989
E_a (kJ/mol)	23.004	23.004	23.004	23.004

Fig.9 shows the variation of the initial diffusion coefficient as a function of immersion temperature. It appears that this variation of the initial diffusion coefficient D_0 is consistent with the Arrhenius law [14]. Thus, we can express the diffusion coefficient in the form of equation (9).

$$D_0(T) = d_0 e^{\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right)} \quad (9)$$

where

d_0 : index of water permeability in the material

E_a : diffusion activation energy

R : ideal gases constant

T : immersion temperature in degrees Kelvin

Fig.9. Variation of D_0 with temperature.

From the approximation shown in Fig.9, we obtain the following evolution of D_0 with water temperature T (in degrees Kelvin):

$$D_0(T) = 0.1 e^{\left(\frac{-2766.7}{T}\right)} \quad (10)$$

Then, from the approximation shown in Fig.10, we obtain the following evolution of ω with water temperature T (in degrees Kelvin):

$$\omega(T) = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-17} e^{\left(\frac{T}{10.8}\right)} \quad (11)$$

The diffusion coefficient finally writes as follows:

$$D(T, t) = 0.1 e^{\left(-\frac{2766.7}{T} + 6.5 \cdot 10^{-17} t^2 e^{\left(\frac{T}{10.8}\right)}\right)} \quad (12)$$

Fig.10. Variation of ω with temperature.

Fig.11 illustrates the comparison between experimental results and simulation results obtained using the analytical solution of the diffusion equation (see equation 6) taking into account a variable diffusion coefficients calculated from equation 12.

It can be clear seen that, for the 4 water temperatures considered, the correlation is much better than when using a constant diffusion coefficient.

Fig.11. Experimental results of water isothermal diffusion compared with the new analytical model of diffusion for temperatures 20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C, and 80 °C.

7 Implementation in the FEA model

The next step consists of applying the variable diffusion coefficient introduced in the previous section in the FEA simulations and comparing the results obtained with experimental data.

Fig.12 shows the comparison between the experimental results of hydrothermal aging, at the 4 temperatures considered in previous sections, with FEA simulations, using the new diffusion model with a variable diffusion coefficient. These results illustrate that, as expected, the correlation with experimental data is much better than when using a model with a constant diffusion coefficient, and this for the 4 water temperatures considered,.

Fig.12. Experimental results of isothermal diffusion compared with FEA simulations based on the new model of diffusion for temperatures 20 °C, 40 °C, 60 °C, and 80 °C.

8 Conclusion

In this contribution, the kinetics of water diffusion in a polypropylene composite reinforced with short hemp fibers is studied. Several immersion tests with distilled water in an isothermal bath have been conducted and it appears that the absorption process cannot be described using Fick's model. Indeed, the first stage of diffusion over the square root of time is clearly nonlinear. A new model, based on the introduction of a variable diffusion coefficient in Fick's diffusion equation is successfully considered. Experimental results show that the diffusion

coefficient strongly depends on water temperature, and therefore, the time required to reach saturation also strongly depends on water temperature.

9 References

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